

CARBON SEQUESTRATION THROUGH AGRICULTURE: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The increase in greenhouse gases (GHG) content in the atmosphere in the last century. Carbon naturally moves, or cycles, between the atmosphere and vegetation, soils, and the oceans over time scales ranging from years to millennia and longer. Process of transfer and secure storage of atmospheric CO₂ into other longlived C pools that would otherwise be emitted or remain in the atmosphere is called 'carbon sequestration'. Research studies on different crops, regardless of the climatic condition indicates that tillage operation, integrated nutrient management, appropriate cropping system, growing cover crops, green manure crops, crop rotations, residue retention, mulching, agroforestry systems and soil restoration activities are frequently verified in improving the soil organic carbon and nutrients content of the soil.

Keywords: Carbon; sequestration; mulching; C pool

INTRODUCTION

The increase in greenhouse gases (GHG) content in the atmosphere in the last century has created a generalized concern for the potential consequences of maintaining this rate (IPCC, 2007). The best tool that we have so far is to look at current trends and estimate what the worst-case scenario could look like if those trends are maintained. The most important greenhouse gases are carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and chloro fluoro carbons (CFCs) and 399.5 ppm, 1834 ppb, 328 ppb, 820 ppt are the concentrations of these gases in the atmosphere respectively (IPCC, 2016). They are produced naturally and anthropogenically. Thus, GHG levels have been increasing since the times of industrial revolution (IPCC, 2016). Potential adverse impacts include sea-level rise; increased frequency and intensity of wildfires, floods, droughts, and tropical storms; changes in the amount, timing, and distribution of rain, snow, and runoff; and disturbance of coastal marine and other ecosystems (USGS, 2008). Awareness and concern on this issue has created a generalized interest on finding effective ways to reduce net GHG emissions. There are three different ways to accomplish this task (Lal 2008): reducing global energy use, using an alternative no-carbon source of energy, and sequestering carbon from point sources or from the atmosphere through natural and engineered systems. The use of ecosystems that naturally capture and sequester carbon is, as of today, one of the most efficient and cost-effective approaches to counteract the GHG emissions (IPCC 2007).

CARBON CYCLE

Carbon naturally moves, or cycles, between the atmosphere and vegetation, soils, and the oceans over time scales ranging from years to millennia and longer. Human activities have increased the transfer of carbon as CO₂ to the atmosphere. Although some of this anthropogenic CO₂ is removed from the atmosphere by the natural uptake processes ("sinks") of the carbon cycle, much of it remains in the atmosphere and causes rising CO₂ concentrations. The goal of deliberate carbon sequestration is to decrease the net flux of CO₂ to the atmosphere by sequestering carbon in the oceans, vegetation, soils, and porous rock formations (USGS, 2008).

CARBON SEQUESTRATION

Emission rates from fossil fuel combustion increased by 40 % between 1980 and 2000 (Wofsy, 2001). Yet, the amount of CO₂ accumulating in the atmosphere remained the same because the excess CO₂ released is being removed by oceans, forests, soils and other ecosystems (Battle et al., 2000; Pacala, 2001). This process of transfer and secure storage of atmospheric CO₂ into other longlived C pools that would otherwise be emitted or remain in the atmosphere is called 'carbon sequestration'. The objective of an anthropogenically driven C sequestration process is to balance the global C budget such that future economic growth is based on a 'C-neutral' strategy of no net gain in atmospheric C pool (Lackner, 2003; Pacala and Socolow, 2004) There are several technological options for sequestration of atmospheric CO₂ into one of the other global pools. The choice of one or a combination of several technologies is important for formulating

energy policies for future economic growth and development at national and global scales. These options can be grouped into two broad categories: abiotic and biotic sequestration.

Abiotic sequestration.

Abiotic sequestration is based on physical and chemical reactions and engineering techniques without intervention of living organisms (e.g. plants, microbes). The abiotic strategy of C sequestration in oceanic and geological structures has received considerable attention (Freund & Ormerod, 1997) because theoretically abiotic sequestration has a larger sink capacity than biotic sequestration. Rapid progress is being made in developing/testing technologies for CO₂ capture, transport and injection (Kerr, 2001).

Oceanic injection

Injection of a pure CO₂ stream deep in the ocean is a possibility that has been widely considered by engineers for about three decades. Following the initial proposal in the late 1970s, there has been considerable progress in oceanic injection of CO₂. To be stable and minimize outgassing, CO₂ must be injected at great depths. Therefore, liquefied CO₂ separated from industrial sources can be injected into the ocean by one of the following four techniques: (i) it is injected below 1000 m from a manifold lying at the ocean floor, and being lighter than water, it rises to approximately 1000 m depth forming a droplet plume; (ii) it is also injected as a denser CO₂-seawater mixture at 500–1000 m depth, and the mixture sinks into the deeper ocean; (iii) it is discharged from a large pipe towed behind a ship; and (iv) it is pumped into a depression at the bottom of the ocean floor forming a CO₂ lake. Liquefied CO₂ injected at approximately 3000 m depth is believed to remain stable (O'Connor et al., 2001). The oceanic sink capacity for CO₂ sequestration is estimated at 5000–10 000 Pg C, exceeding the estimated fossil fuel reserves (Herzog et al., 2002). However, CO₂ injection may also have some adverse effects on deep sea biota (Seibel & Walsh, 2001). In addition to the economics, the issue of stability of such an injection must be addressed owing to the increased stratification of the ocean water column and its turn over through natural processes.

Geological injection

This involves capture, liquefaction, transport and injection of industrial CO₂ into deep geological strata. The CO₂ may be injected in coal seams, old oil wells (to increase yield), stable rock strata or saline aquifers (Baines & Worden, 2004). Saline aquifers are underground strata of very porous sediments filled with brackish (saline) water. In general, saline aquifers are located below the freshwater reservoirs with an impermeable layer in between. Industrial CO₂ can be pumped into the aquifer, where it is sequestered hydrodynamically and by reacting with other dissolved salts to form carbonates. Carbon dioxide is injected in a supercritical state that has much lower density and viscosity than the liquid brine that it displaces. In situ, it forms a gas-like phase and also dissolves in the aqueous phase, creating a multiphase multicomponent environment. Injecting CO₂ into reservoirs in which it displaces oil or gas could be an economic strategy of enhanced oil recovery (EOR). Production from oil and gas fields, which has been in decline, is raised by CO₂-enhanced recovery (Klusman, 2003). This strategy of CO₂ sequestration is used in Texas, USA, to inject 20 million Mg of CO₂ yr⁻¹ at a price of \$10–\$15 Mg⁻¹ (Lackner, 2003). The technique is also used in offshore oil wells in Norway. In a strict sense, however, this is not sequestration when the CO₂ injected is extracted from underground wells. The CO₂ can also be injected into unmineable coal seams where CH₄ is absorbed. Injected CO₂ is absorbed onto coal twice as much as CH₄, and the process enhances the gas recovery of coal bed CH₄ (CBM). Principal concerns about geological sequestration, similar to that of the oceanic, are (Schrag, 2007): (i) reliability of storage of vast quantities of CO₂ in geological strata and (ii) the cost. Some have argued that risks of leakage are low. However, to date, a few direct injections of CO₂ have been made on a commercial scale although the Regional Carbon Sequestration Partnership project of US DOE is planning for several demonstrations during 2008–2009. Similar to oceanic injection, cost and leakage are principal issues of geological sequestration which need to be resolved. Owing to the low density and viscosity and injection under supercritical conditions, the risks of CO₂ leakage through confining strata may be higher than currently injected liquid wastes (Tsang et al., 2002). In addition, the chemical interactions of CO₂ with the geological formations may have to be considered in formulating guidelines for appropriate regulatory and monitoring controls.

Scrubbing and mineral carbonation

Mineral carbonation is achieved through mimicry of natural inorganic chemical transformation of CO₂ (Fan & Park, 2004). It involves transformation of industrial strength CO₂ emissions into CaCO₃, MgCO₃ and other

minerals in the form of geologically and thermodynamically stable mineral carbonates. It is a two-stage process: scrubbing and mineral carbonation. Scrubbing, the process of chemical absorption of CO₂ using an amine or carbonate solvent, is the most widely used method of carbon capture. The CO₂ is purified by passing through an absorption column containing amine solvent. Other solvents used are K₂CO₃, lithium silicate, ceramic and nickel-based compounds. Pure CO₂ gas, recovered by heating the CO₂-rich amine, is re-precipitated through mineral carbonation. Carbonates thus formed are stable rock in which CO₂ is sequestered forever. Aqueous mineral carbonation reactions leading to the formation of magnesite (MgCO₃), olivine (Mg₂SiO₄) and serpentine (Mg₂Si₂O₅(OH)₄) are as follows (Gerdemann et al., 2003). All these reactions occur in nature and can be replicated in industrial settings. The industrial process of mineral carbonation has been described by Lackner et al., (1996). The process uses a slurry of fine particle-sized mineral in water, at solid concentrations of 15–30%. Dissolution of the mineral and subsequent carbonation occur in a single operation as per the following theorized reactions (Gerdemann et al., 2004). Geological studies have shown that reserves of ultramafic (ultrabasic) minerals are sufficient to provide raw materials for mineral carbonation of industrial emissions for long time (Goff et al., 2000). However, these are geological reactions and occur at slow rate. The challenge lies in increasing the rate of reaction by decreasing the particle size, increasing temperature and pressure and using catalytic agents (Fan & Park, 2004). Increasing the rate of reactions, however, requires energy and is expensive.

Biotic sequestration

Biotic sequestration is based on managed intervention of higher plants and micro-organisms in removing CO₂ from the atmosphere. It differs from management options which reduce emission or offset emission. Increasing use efficiency of resources (e.g. water, energy) is another option for managing the terrestrial C pool. Some biotic sequestration options are briefly described below

Oceanic sequestration

There are several biological processes leading to C sequestration in the ocean through photosynthesis. Phytoplankton photosynthesis is one such mechanism, which fixes approximately 45 Pg C yr⁻¹ (Falkowski et al., 2000). Some of the particulate organic material formed by phytoplankton is deposited at the ocean floor and is thus sequestered. Availability of Fe is one of the limiting factors on phytoplankton growth in oceanic ecosystems. Thus, several studies have assessed the importance of Fe fertilization on biotic CO₂ sequestration in the ocean (Falkowski, 1997). It is also argued that incremental C could be sold as credits in the developing global C marketplace. Similar to deep injection, ocean fertilization may also change the ecology of the ocean. However, with the current state of knowledge, the topic of ocean fertilization remains a debatable issue (Johnson & Karl, 2002).

Terrestrial sequestration

Transfer of atmospheric CO₂ into biotic and pedologic C pools is called terrestrial C sequestration. Of the 8.6 Pg C yr⁻¹ emitted into the atmosphere, only 3.5 Pg or 40% of the anthropogenically emitted CO₂ remains in the atmosphere primarily owing to unspecified terrestrial sinks which sequester atmospheric CO₂ and play an important role in the global C cycle. Terrestrial ecosystems constitute a major C sink owing to the photosynthesis and storage of CO₂ in live and dead organic matter. Owing to its numerous ancillary benefits (e.g. improved soil and water quality, restoration of degraded ecosystems, increased crop yield), terrestrial C sequestration is often termed as win or no-regrets strategy (Lal et al., 2003). It offers multiple benefits even without the threat of global climate change. The soil pool is therefore the most suitable carbon pool to manage and maximize in a cost-effective manner. Most carbon sequestration studies have been done in agricultural soils (Lal et al., 1998) since, agricultural soils are easily manageable through adoption of agricultural practices.

AGRICULTURE PRACTICES TO INCREASE CARBON SEQUESTRATION

Research studies on different crops, regardless of the climatic condition indicates that tillage operation, integrated nutrient management, appropriate cropping system, growing cover crops, green manure crops, crop rotations, residue retention, mulching, agroforestry systems and soil restoration activities are frequently verified in improving the soil organic carbon and nutrients content of the soil.

Tillage

Soil disturbance from tillage is a major cause of organic matter depletion and reduction in the number and stability of soil aggregates when native ecosystems are converted to agriculture. No-till (NT)

cropping systems usually exhibit increased aggregation and soil organic matter relative to conventional tillage (CT). However, the extent of soil organic matter changes in response to NT management varies between soils and the mechanisms of organic matter stabilization in NT systems are unclear. We evaluated a conceptual model which links the turnover of aggregates to soil organic matter dynamics in NT and CT systems; we argue that the rate of macroaggregate formation and degradation (i.e. aggregate turnover) is reduced under NT compared to CT and leads to a formation of stable microaggregates in which carbon is stabilized and sequestered in the long term. Therefore, the link between macroaggregate turnover, microaggregate formation, and C stabilization within microaggregates partly determines the observed soil organic matter increases under NT (Six et al., 2000). Concentration of soil organic C after 9 years of tillage experiments is shown in Fig. 8. No-till resulted in significantly ($p < 0.01$) greater soil organic C in the top 4 cm of soil, which was 57.8% greater than that in the top 4 cm of the plow-till. In the second 4 cm depth, organic C concentration was 15.1% greater than the plow-till. In the 8–30 cm depths, the organic C concentration was not different ($p = 0.25$) among tillage systems. The pattern for organic C distribution in the ridge-till treatment was similar to that seen in the no-till, with 44.2% greater organic C in the top 4 cm, and 12.9% higher in the 4–8 cm depth (Zibilske et al., 2002). In the 0–5 cm soil depth, total SOC concentration was significantly greater in the NT-11 and NT-20 phases compared with the NT-4, NT-1 and CT phases. Furthermore, SOC concentration in the NT-4 phase was significantly greater than in the NT-1 and CT phases. However, below 5 cm soil depth no significant differences were found among treatments. The stratification of SOC on soil surface increased with the time under NT. In the 0–5 and 20–30 cm soil layers, SOC concentration values ranged between 8.6 and 10.5, 8.5 and 20.0, 7.1 and 24.0 and 6.5 and 24.0 g C kg⁻¹ dry soil in the NT-1, NT-4, NT-11 and NT-20 phases, respectively (Table 1). In the NT-11 and NT-20 phases, SOC concentration among soil depths was significantly different in the next order: 0–5 > 5–10 > 10–20 and 20–30 cm depth. However, in the NT-4 phase differences were only found between 0–5 cm and the rest of the analyzed depths. Moreover, in the NT-1 phase, total SOC concentration did not show any stratification trend with depth. (Bonilla et al., 2013). Stocks of SOC under NT were significantly higher at 0–20 cm than those under CT. It is concluded that NT farming does not necessarily store SOC more than CT soils for the upper soil layer (Huang et al., 2016).

Nutrient management

Organic sources of fertilizer are reservoirs of plant nutrients and organic carbon, and hence amendment with adequate and quality manure ultimately enhances the soil nutrients and SOC stocks of the soil. Ding X et al., (2012) has found that application of graded rates of manure from lower to higher level significantly enhanced total SOC as compared with control. The C storage from the top 20 cm depth with the rate of 7.5, 15, and 22 t/ha was increased from 3.19% to 12.5%, 14.5%, and 18.2%, respectively, over the unfertilized control. Under soybean–wheat systems, NPK application had a significant effect on C sequestration, which was further increased with annual NPK+FYM application. About 20% the gross C input contributed to SOC accumulation. Although the plots under NPK+FYM had higher SOC build up (and, hence, carbon sequestration potential) than other treatments (Bhattacharyya et al., 2009). Application of organic and inorganic amendments had significant effect on distribution of different carbon pool and their share at surface depth ($p \leq 0.05$). Among nutrient management practices, organic treatment (incorporation of crop residue along with FYM and biofertilizers) significantly increased Cfrac1 ($p = 0.001$), Cfrac2 ($p = 0.04$) and Cfrac3 ($p \leq 0.01$) over control and inorganic (NPKSZnB) but not the Cfrac4 ($p = 0.812$). The distribution of different carbon fractions followed the order Cfrac3 > Cfrac1 > Cfrac4 > Cfrac2 in surface depth (Ghosh et al., 2012). The data pertaining to the effect of long-term application of different nutrient management practices on total soil organic carbon under LTFE are presented in Table 4. Total SOC varied from 1.18 to 1.96 per cent. The total SOC was significantly higher in integrated treatment T8 (100 per cent NPK + FYM @ 5 t ha⁻¹) than that in all other treatments. This was followed by T10 where *Sesbania aculeata* was grown and incorporated at the site before the crop. TOC value was significantly lower in T12 (Absolute control (No fertilizers/manures)) than that in all other treatments (Sumayya, 2016).

Cover crops

Through formation of a quick and protective ground cover, cover crops improve SOC content, enhance soil biodiversity, improve soil structure and minimize risks of soil erosion. Growing of cover crops like rye, hairy vetch, and crimson clover in tomato egg plant cropping system given a higher soil organic carbon (17.9, 17.0, 17.5 Mg ha⁻¹ respectively) compare to control (15.4 Mg ha⁻¹) which was grown no cover crops (Sainju et al., 2003).

Crop rotation

Crop rotation has many agronomic, economic and environmental benefits compared to monoculture cropping system. Appropriate crop rotation improves organic matter, soil structure, soil degradation, grain yields and greater farm profitability in the long run. In India, the major cropping systems are cereal-cereal (rice-rice, cereal-cereal-cereal I (rice-wheat-maize), cereal-cereal-legume (rice-wheat-green gram), legume-cereal (pulse-wheat) and oilseed-cereal (oilseed-wheat). Conventional agriculture normally reduces the SOC of the surface or plough layer. Conservation tillage systems increase SOC level. The data indicated that rice-wheat-green gram crop sequence has greater SOC restoration than rice-wheat followed by rice-green gram and rice-mustard possibly due to inclusion of legume in cereal-cereal cropping system (Sharma and Bali, 2000). In longterm study in Indo-Gangetic alluvial soils with rice based cropping system C- sequestration was maximum in rice-wheat-jute system (535 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) at Barrackpore followed by Rice-mustard-sesame (414 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) than rice-fallow-rice (402 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) at CRRI, Cuttack (Mandal et al., 2008). Inclusion of pulses in the rice-based system increased C_{frac1} compared with the rice-wheat system. Maximum and significant ($p \leq 0.05$) increase in C_{frac1} (64%) at surface depth was observed under both rice-wheat-mung bean and rice-wheat-rice-chickpea systems. The effect of cropping system on C_{frac2} was also significant ($p \leq 0.05$) at surface depth. The rice-wheat-rice-chickpea system resulted in greater accumulation of C_{frac2} in surface layer. Inclusion of mung bean in the rice-wheat system led to significantly ($p \leq 0.01$) higher C_{frac3} as compared with other cropping systems in surface depth. C_{frac4} did not vary significantly ($p > 0.05$) with cropping systems (Ghosh et al., 2012).

Green manures

Similar to other sources of organic fertilizer, green manure improved the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil. Soil organic carbon, N content, soil aggregation, reduced soil bulk density and increased infiltration rate of soil. Field experiment was conducted for 7 years continuously to evaluate the influence of combined application of organic and inorganic fertilizer on soil fertility buildup and nutrient uptake in mint (*Mentha arvensis*) and mustard (*Brassica juncea*) cropping sequence. Maximum organic carbon was observed under full supply of organic manure (T₂; FYM at 20 t ha⁻¹) averaged across all the Stages of cropping sequence. It was increased by 38, 50, and 51% in T₂ in Stages I (after mint harvest/presowing of dhaincha), II (after incorporation of dhaincha (*Sesbania aculeata*)/presowing of mustard), and III (after harvest of mustard /preplanting of mint), respectively, over their respective controls. In general, magnitude of organic carbon was recorded higher in Stage II after green manuring of *Sesbania* compared with Stages I and III (Chand et al., 2006).

Crop residue

In agriculture we are producing lot of crop residues and most of this residue are being burnt, instead of burning, using crop residue as mulch can sequester more SOC through conserving water, reducing soil erosion, improving soil structure, enhancing SOC concentration. The influence of crop residue treatment on organic carbon is presented in Table 10. Significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher organic matter levels were detected on soils treated with rice straw and legume residue compared to the soil without residue treatment and that with burnt rice husk treatment. The highest organic matter levels on such plots were as a result of the decomposition of the crop residue. This is because organic matter is the major product of crop residue decomposition. The reduction of organic matter level on burnt rice husk treated plots was due to losses in organic carbon during the burning process. Organic carbon normally constitutes 58% of soil organic matter; hence burning reduced much of the organic carbon concentration of the rice husk. The study showed that returning crop residue to the soil could be beneficial; in enhancing soil organic carbon. It was specifically concluded that the use of adequate quantity of rice straw, burnt rice husk and legume residues improves the fertility status of the soil (Ogbodo, 2011). Ghimire et al., (2012). Suggest that no-tillage with crop residue application would result in distinctly higher carbon sequestration at upper soil depths than under other tillage and residue combinations.

Mulching

Covering the soil with any mulching material sequester soil organic carbon through reducing water loss, reducing soil erosion, improving soil structure, enhancing SOC. Natural organic mulch eventually breaks down and adds organic material to the soil. The increase of the amount of soil organic carbon (SOC) is regarded as the main advantage of organic mulches. The aim of investigation was to evaluate the effect of different organic mulches on the content of SOC. The field experiment was

carried out at Lithuania, Europe. The following treatments were applied: mulch: (1) without mulch, (2) straw, (3) peat, (4) sawdust, and (5) grass. The influence of organic mulches was investigated in 2004-2009 and their residual effect in 2010, 2011. Here the data of 2008-2011 are presented. A higher content of SOC was established in all mulched experimental plots compared with the unmulched plots. A significant influence of peat mulch was observed during the whole period reported since peat contains more organic carbon (Bajoriene, 2013). After five cropping seasons significantly higher carbon concentrations in the 0–2.5 and 2.5–5 cm soil layers were observed under the no-tillage and mulching treatments compared with the treatments without residues and conventional tillage. However, no significant differences between treatments were observed at greater depths. When expressed on a surface basis, substantial differences in soil carbon content of the 0–20 cm topsoil layer were observed after five years between treatments. Carbon contents under NT+1.5Mg ha⁻¹ Mulch and NT+4.5Mg ha⁻¹ Mulch were, respectively, about 14% and 20% higher compared with the NT without mulch treatment. On the other hand, the carbon content under conventional tillage (CT) was 7% lower when compared with the NT without mulch (Scopel et al., 2005).

Agroforestry

Currently we are in such a situation that we can not increase cultivable area by reducing the forest area and vice-versa, so agroforestry system is one of the efficient techniques to reduce green house gas concentrations in the atmosphere and to increase the carbon sequestration as the trees are efficient absorbers of CO₂. And it alternately adds lot of leaf litter into soil there by it improves soil fertility and finally it results in higher crop yields. Alternate land use systems, viz., agro-forestry, agrohorticulture, and agro-silviculture, are more remunerative for SOC restoration as compared to sole cropping system. In northeast hill regions of India, the above three land use systems practice reduce soil erosion and loss of SOC considerably. In a 6-year study, organic carbon content was about double in agro-horticultural and agro-forestry systems as compared to sole cropping (Das and Itnal, 1994). In a 20-years study, the cultivation of *Prosopis juliflora*, *Acacia nilotica*, *Eucalyptus tereticornis*, *Terminalis arjuna* and *Albizia lebbek* increased about 6-10-fold greater SOC. In this study, it was observed that C-sequestration was relatively low under *E. tereticornis* (168 kg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) (Singh, 1994).

Soil restoration practices

The degraded lands will be of low fertile soils and it leads to low biomass production and it ultimately leads to low carbon capture (carbon sequestration), so following of some soil restoration activities viz. Cultivation of pastures, application of organic manures and afforestation are known to improve carbon sequestration. Land disturbance during mining results in loss of soil organic carbon (SOC). Reclamation of mine lands can lead to recuperation and sequestration of SOC. The SOC thus accumulated, not only replenishes SOC losses but may also offset additional carbon di-oxide (CO₂) emission. The assessment of the above was done on a chronosequence of reclaimed mine soils comprising pasture with topsoil application. The chronosequence consisted of reclaimed mine sites, 0 to 25 years old, keeping 1997 as the base year. The data show that there was a drastic loss of SOC during mining, and mine soil reclamation over time enhanced SOC pools to original levels. The SOC content increased from 9.2 Mg ha⁻¹ in the beginning of reclamation period to 55.4 Mg ha⁻¹ after 25 years for the 0-15 cm depth. The SOC content of the pasture control site were 30.3 Mg ha⁻¹. Temporal change in losses and gains in the SOC contents of reclaimed sites with respect to the pasture control site over the reclamation duration are shown in Fig. 13. In comparison to an initial loss of 21 Mg ha⁻¹, there was a gain of 25 Mg ha⁻¹ after 25 years for the 0-15 cm depth. It is, however, important to note that the magnitude of the loss and gain depend on the SOC content of the control site. There was significant difference in SOC content of the pasture control site and 25-year-old reclaimed sites (Akala and Lal, 1997).

CONCLUSION

Carbon sequestration helps to mitigate climate change as it helps to reduce CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere. Agricultural practices like no tillage, cropping system, residue incorporation, mulching and soil restoration practices enhances carbon sequestration in agricultural fields and it also improves physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil.

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